

SIOS core data	Link to geosphere
SCD 1.1. WIND SPEED	Topographic control
SCD 1.2. WIND DIRECTION	Topographic control
SCD 1.14. CARBON DIOXIDE	Natural release, carbon capture and storage
SCD 1.17. METHANE	Natural release, controlled by subsurface geology, energy source
SCD 2.1. GLACIER MASS BALANCE	Topographic and climatic control
SCD 2.2. GLACIER ELEVATION	Topographic and climatic control
SCD 2.5. ACTIVE LAYER	Topographic, climatic and heat flow control
SCD 2.6. PERMAFROST	Topographic, climatic and heat flow control. Characterization by various geophysical techniques and drilling (LYBCO2 DH8).
SCD 2.7. GROUND ICE	Topographic, climatic and heat flow control. Characterization by various geophysical techniques and drilling (LYBCO2 DH8).
SCD 4.2. SEA LEVEL RISE	Absolute vs relative sea level rise when land uplift is accounted for.
SCD 4.3. OCEAN CURRENTS	Bathymetric control on the circulation patterns (e.g., opening of Fram Strait)
SCD 4.4. SEA SURFACE TEMPERATURE	Past global climate change, for instance during mass extinctions.

References

University of California UGC Berkely (2024) Understanding Global Change - Infographic. <https://ugc.berkeley.edu/what-is-global-change/infographic/>. Accessed 6 Jun 2024.